
A Study on Correlation With Entrepreneurial Innovation and Gross Domestic Product of Selected States

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Abstract:

The creativity among the human being is the important for being success in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are always trying to searching new and useful ways and means to make human life happier and bring materially richer. Entrepreneurs are taking efforts for rising standard of living of the people through launching innovative ideas in business and industry. Such peoples are real creators of wealth and prosperity. Providing new kind of product and services, upgrading and modernising the existing process of production of commodities is treated as innovation. Entrepreneur has perception and also aware about the wants and desires of consumer and try to increase the satisfaction level. Entrepreneurs are common people but they are thinking different. They are different from ordinary people in regards with vision, attitude, perspectives and efforts. Most of the entrepreneurs are self-oriented about their overall business activity and have complete and comprehensive understanding. They try to work out solution on troubles of common people by innovative way. Entrepreneurship transforms problem in to opportunity. They are not order takers on the other hand they the order makers. This paper is prepared for developing healthy competition among the state in innovation and it will be help full for strengthening entrepreneurship of India.

Key words: creativity, innovation, new idea, sustain, level up.

Introduction:

Entrepreneurship and innovation are closely related concepts that involve creating new ideas and putting them into action. Innovation can lead to higher productivity, meaning that the same input generates a greater output. As productivity rises, more goods and services are produced – in other words, the economy grows. Entrepreneurs have perception and also aware about the wants and desires of consumer and try to increase the satisfaction level. Entrepreneurs are common people but they are thinking different. Innovation allows businesses to thrive as it brings in creative solutions to problems and allows the business owners to apply their creativity to the max to make their presence valuable in the market.

Innovation is crucial for success in business since both humans and customers are attracted to new things or ideas. Time must be given to finding innovative and practical solutions to improve human happiness and material well-being. Entrepreneurs are working to raise the standard of living for the population by introducing novel concepts in trade and business. These affects actually produce riches and prosperity. Innovation is defined as the creation of novel goods and services as well as the improvement and modernisation of the current methods for producing them. Innovation allows companies to make continuous improvements and helps in enhancing the creativity of the business.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the role of innovation in industry and gross domestic product.
2. To research the GDP shares and innovation rankings of a few states.
3. To offer advice on how to innovate effectively.

Methodology of the study:

This paper is based on secondary sources of information, including books, study guides, journals, government papers, websites, and to some extent, the researchers' own first-hand observations.

Conceptual framework:

1. **Gross Domestic product:** Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a measure of a country's economic output. It's calculated by adding the value of all goods and services produced within a country over a specific period of time. GDP is used to compare the health of economies across countries and over time. Innovation is a key driver of economic growth, which is measured by gross domestic product (GDP). Innovation can boost productivity, consumer spending, and profits, and it can also create new jobs.
2. **Correlation with Gross Domestic Product (GDP):** One of the major benefits of innovation is its contribution to economic growth. Simply put, innovation can lead to higher productivity, meaning that the same input generates a greater output. As productivity rises, more goods and services are produced – in other words, the economy grows.

If nations with environments conducive to innovation witness higher GDP growth rates than their peers who lack these conditions. By fostering innovation, we can create entirely new industries and revenue streams.

1. **Increased productivity:** Innovation can increase productivity by automating tasks or by making machines more useful to humans.
2. **New industries:** Innovation can create new industries and revenue streams, such as the internet, which has changed how businesses operate.
3. **Consumer confidence:** Innovation can boost consumer confidence and spending.

India can encourage innovation following ways:

Research and development: Countries can encourage innovation by supporting research and development.

Education: Countries with a highly educated workforce can invest more in innovation.

Intellectual property management: Countries can encourage innovation by protecting intellectual property rights.

Competition and trade: Countries can encourage innovation by promoting competition and international trade.

Concept of Innovation: Innovation is idea of bringing new product and idea in business. Innovation frequently sounds more like a magic formula for business success than a genuine business concept.

But problem-solving is all that innovation is, really.

Finding novel solutions to problems for which there is no existing answer, an inadequate solution, or a solution that is only accessible to a certain group of customers. Innovation has the power to alter how that industry operates. It might even entirely change the sector. It is essential for maintaining the company's viability and market competitiveness.

The ability to innovate will be necessary for entrepreneurs to deal with the entrepreneurship, innovation, and creativity go hand in hand. It is essential for maintaining the company's viability and

market competitiveness. To meet the problems of the market, entrepreneurs must possess the quality of innovation. If you want to run a successful business, you must first be somewhat original in your approach and possess any viewpoints, ideas, and opinions necessary to introduce a unique concept into the market that will help you draw clients to your goods and services. Systematic innovation will enable you to gain an edge over your competitors and improve the profitability of your business. It has become necessary to invest in research and development and talent management.

Innovation functions in entrepreneurship.

- 1. Creative Development:** Innovation helps organizations grow by introducing original solutions to issues and enabling business owners to use their imagination to the fullest in order to differentiate their offerings from those of competitors.
- 2. Constant Improvement:** Innovation helps businesses become more creative and enables them to make ongoing improvements.
- 3. Deliver the best product or service:** In line with the kaizen philosophy of “Good Change” or “improvement” in relation with lean technique and its tenets, it means constant improvement.
- 4.** One of the most crucial aspects of operating a corporation is implementing fresh, constructive modifications and launching new goods. However, organizations should also maintain and improve the quality of their existing products. Where creativity is really important
- 5. Reacting to Trends and Competition:** Adopting market trends and facing fierce competition both require innovation. Innovation is important regarding cope up with the market trends and also face the tough competition. Having an idea of the future trends and being able to keep

up with them helps the grooming the business.

- 6. To boost the sale:** any company with an inventive culture gives its products a special touch. Additionally, it aids in the organization's increased market exposure.
- 7. Social media promotion:** social media is a fantastic medium for increasing brand awareness for the business. This is not only aids in marketing but also draws attention to the business's creative idea from the general public. Business houses can launch their creative campaigns through social platforms to that will draw project image among the customer as well as regular individuals.

Innovation implementation Philosophy:

These idea focusses on changing management perspective in order to apply innovation in company.

- A. Viewing challenge as a change
- B. Find additional resources to solve the issue
- C. Resist maintaining the status quo.
- D. Form an evaluation mindset regarding the causes of adaptive change.
- E. Find solutions when you discover errors.
- F. Encourage everyone to participate by sharing your ideas.
- G. Determine the underlying reasons for innovation and change.
- H. Gather data and suggestion form the group
- I. Incorporate imagination in to minor upgrades.
- J. Use creativity in little improvements.
- K. Create culture akin to Kaizen.

Measurement Criteria for innovation:

Innovation is crucial to the survival and growth of business in the Indian economy in order to comprehend Indian's current innovation state. The NITI Ayog ha taken the initiative to assess India's performance. Seven criteria have been

chosen by NITI Ayog to assess the performance of innovation. By using these criteria, it may be able to foster healthy rivalry between the states to raise their performance in terms of the innovation index.

Knowledge partner, the business environment, safety precautions, the legal environment, human resources and capital,

output of knowledge and knowledge dissemination.

Innovation index is an extensive tool assessing and developing India's ecosystem. Niti Aayog has taken lead for developing state level innovation index. In the context of the Indian economy, the primary goal is to create an ecosystem and a plan for rising the states innovation index.

Table No -1: In India, innovation and GDP Share are ranked by state

Rank No.	State	Innovation Score	GDP in (Lakh Crore)	Rank in India
1.	Karnataka	18.01	25	04
2.	Telangana	17.66	28.03	09
3.	Haryana	16.35	11.2	12
4.	Maharashtra	16.06	38.79	01
5.	Tamil Nadu	15.69	28.3	02
6.	Punjab	15.35	6.98	16
7.	Uttar Pradesh	14.22	24.29	05
8.	Kerala	13.67	11.02	11
9.	Andhra Pradesh	13.32	24.29	08
10.	Jharkhand	13.10	4.23	19
11.	West Bengal	12.98	17.29	06
12.	Rajasthan	12.88	15.07	07
13.	Madhya Pradesh	12.74	13.87	10
14.	Gujarat	12.41	25.62	03
15.	Bihar	11.58	8.59	15
16.	Odisha	11.42	8.65	14
17.	Chhattisgarh	10.97	5.07	18

(Source: Niti Ayog report of innovation 2021 and report of GDP in India)

Graphical representation of state wise ranking in innovation in India

It has been determined that Karnataka holds the top spot in the large state category of the Indian innovation index. Chhattisgarh, on the other hand, is at the bottom of the list. In the Indian innovation index, Maharashtra is ranked fifth in terms of industrialization, employment creation and contribution to India's GDP, Maharashtra is basically the top state. However, Maharashtra has not made an effort to encourage innovation. Another state where strong infrastructure is major contributor to success is Gujrat, which ranks first in the NITI Aayog India innovation index's major states category. Because it attracted FDI and significant venture capital agreements, Karnataka is through to have received the highest grade.

Conclusion:

It may be said that is concluded NITI Ayog's efforts in calculating the innovation index led to the realisation that the state of Karnataka had attained the highest rank in innovation.

1. Maharashtra is first in GDP contribution and third in terms of area. This state is renowned as India's creative capital and is a leader in the engineering and cinema, IT, automotive and service sectors.

Maharashtra is ranked fifth in the innovation index for India. Maharashtra basically leads the way in terms of industrialization, employment creation, and contribution to India's GDP.

However, Maharashtra has not taken the lead in fostering innovation.

2. Gujrat ranks fourth in terms of GDP and fifteenth in terms of innovation index. The state's main industry is agriculture, although it also depends on the chemical, cotton, milk and dairy, and sugarcane industries for income.

3. Managers should create an innovation strategy that outlines how their business will approach innovation activities and how the ecosystem will support to plan as whole.
4. Benchmarking techniques should be used by all industries: It is a method for comparing an organization's best and most innovative practices to those of competitors when evaluating their processes, services, and products. The group receives this knowledge from this area.
5. Government and non-government organisations should take the lead in developing fresh concepts and adding value to goods and services.
6. Supporting centres for innovation and incubation (III Centre) to find amazing, unique ideas that need the right environment to thrive. The HR department should particularly encourage talented and innovative individual for research and innovation. Small modification or additions are made to existing goods, procedures, or services at the primary stage. Then innovation might advance gradually and eventually the industry might accept this new shift.

Reference:

1. Desai Vasant. (2011). Dynamics of Entrepreneurial Development and Management. New Delhi: Himalaya Publicising House
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Indian_states_and_union_territories_by_GDP
3. https://agits.unifesp.br/images/assets/educa_ebooks/Innovation_Strategy_Harvard_BusinessReview.pdf
4. Pakes, Ariel, 1985, "On Patents, R&D, and the Stock Market Rate of Return,"

- Journal of Political Economy, Vol.93, pp. 390–409.
5. Shejwalkar, P.C. (2011). Entrepreneurship Development. New Delhi: Everest Publishing House. 2nd Edition.
 6. Zachariadis, Marios, 2003 “R&D, Innovation, and Technological Progress: A test of the Schumpeterian Framework without Scale Effects,” Canadian Journal of Economics, Vol 36.
 7. https://www.google.com/search?q=gdp+and+innovation&sca_esv=e74a10221791e7e3&rlz=1C1JJTC_enIN1068IN1070&sxsrf=AHTn8zox9ppq56Njomd30Ibm_8JnKJ9NxGQ%3A17